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METACOGNITIVE EXPECTATIONS

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Abstract

Autonomous cognitive agents must adapt with changing environments to remain effective and robust. Expectations about the world enable an agent to identify an anomalous situation, thus providing the foundation for an appropriate response. While significant work has addressed anomalies in the world, few examples exist that address anomalies within an agent’s own cognition. Such high-level expectations allow an agent to identify anomalous mental situations, which in turn enables the agent to adapt its own knowledge or cognitive processes to complex problems. This paper introduces a new class of expectations called metacognitive expectations. Our contributions are the following: (1) a general formalism for these expectations; (2) an implementation of metacognitive expectations in an agent embodied within a cognitive architecture; and (3) ablation experimental results indicating that an agent equipped with metacognitive expectations outperforms agents operating without such capabilities.

1 Introduction

Expectations are knowledge artifacts that enable agents to check if they are operating as intended. When acting, the agent continuously checks its expectations and takes corrective steps when they are violated. That is, the agent checks if there are *discrepancies* between its expectations and the observations of the state of the world. When such discrepancies are detected, different means of addressing them have been proposed including replanning (i.e., modifying the plan to be executed) and goal reasoning (i.e., changing the goals to be pursued and generating new plans to achieve these goals).

Over the years the notion of expectation has played a central role in the monitoring of plan execution [Pettersson, 2005; Schank, 1982] and in managing comprehension, especially natural language understanding [Schank and Owens, 1987]. For example, research in goal-driven autonomy (GDA) agents (i.e., a class of goal reasoning agents that may change its goals in the event of a discrepancy) has identified different variants of expectations. Some GDA agents compute the expectation based on the effects of the last action executed.

Other GDA agents compute expectations based on the trajectory (i.e., the actions executed so far). Regardless of these variants, a common trait is that agents’ expectations are defined as a function of the observed states and the actions executed so far. That is, they are defined in terms of the *ground level* environment; in terms of objects and events in the world.

In this paper we introduce a new class of expectation: expectations at the metacognitive level or *metacognitive expectations*. When cognitive processes compute expectations about the ground level, we consider the processes a kind of mental action that results in mental objects (i.e., the world-related expectations). These actions and objects then are at the *object level*. Analogously, processes at the *metalevel* can compute expectations of the object level behaviors. Metacognitive agents operate at three distinct levels [Cox and Raja, 2011]:

- The ground level, in which an agent executes actions and makes observations of the state of the world.
- The object level (cognition), in which the agent reasons about the actions performed at the ground-level, the physical objects there and states of those objects.
- The metalevel (metacognition), in which the agent introspectively reasons about the cognition performed at the object level.

Under this perspective, agents such as GDA agents that reason about expectations at the object level (e.g., GDA agents) can be seen as reasoning at the cognitive levels. However, we do not know of any other work that reasons with explicit expectations at the metalevel.

The primary contributions of this work are the following:

- A formalization of the notion of metacognitive expectations
- An implementation of this formalization in the MIDCA metacognitive architecture
- Experiments with two domains from the GDA literature demonstrating the effectiveness of reasoning with expectations at the metalevel. We will use two baselines in our experiment: an agent with replanning capabilities and a GDA agent.

2 Related Work

When an agent encounters a discrepancy, it may perform re-planning: modifying the remaining (i.e., not yet executed) steps of the plan [Hammond, 1990; Cushing and Kambhampati, 2005]. For example, the agent might observe the current state of the world and generate a new plan that achieves the goals from the current state. Some agents aim to make a more careful modification of the remaining plan by taking into account issues such as estimates to complete the plan [Fox *et al.*, 2006]. Regardless of how the plan repair is done, in replanning the goals remain the same. In our work meta-cognitive agents may change the goals that the agent is pursuing.

In contrast to agents performing plan repair, GDA agents may change their goals [Muñoz-Avila *et al.*, 2010; Molineaux *et al.*, 2010]. For example, consider a GDA agent controlling a vessel carrying some valuable cargo to a certain port. If the GDA agent detects a sonar contact that may likely be an enemy submarine, the GDA agent may change its goals to head back to the starting port or head to an alternative port thereby circumventing the potential threat and changing its goals in the process. GDA agents select new goals by performing a cognitive cycle in which they detect the discrepancy at the ground level, generate an explanation for the discrepancy and possibly formulate new goals as a result of that discrepancy. GDA subsumes plan repair because the GDA agent might generate the same goal as before in which case the agent generates a new plan from the current state to achieve this goal. In our work, MIDCA can trigger a process generating new goals at the cognitive level akin to GDA agents. In addition, the MIDCA runs a cycle external to the cognitive level (i.e., metacognition) that supervises the execution at the cognitive level. This cycle may trigger changes in the execution at the cognitive level as a result of discrepancies observed at the cognitive level.

Finally, humans have and exploit expectations concerning their own mental state [Dunlosky *et al.*, 2013b]. Cognitive psychology research has long demonstrated the potential benefit and general characteristics of reasoning about mental state and mechanisms [Flavell, 1979; Flavell and Wellman, 1977]. For example game show contestants can often decide before they retrieve a memory item whether or not they know answers to given questions and demonstrate this by striking buzzers before competitors. Psychologists examined this phenomena and found it to be a robust effect [Reder and Ritter, 1992]. More recently research has shown that even very young students can assess how well they have learned material, can predict memory and problem-solving performance, and can use such metacognitive expectations to choose learning and study strategies [Dunlosky, 2013; Dunlosky *et al.*, 2013a].

3 The MIDCA Metacognitive Architecture

The *Metacognitive Integrated Dual-Cycle Architecture (MIDCA)* is a three level architecture composed of the ground level (where actions and perceptions occur), the object level (where problem-solving and comprehension processes exist), and the metalevel (which introspectively monitors and controls the object-level cognition). The architecture integrates

Figure 1: Schematic action-perception cycle for both object and meta-levels.

both planning and interpretation algorithms; our current implementation incorporates the SHOP2 hierarchical network planner [Nau *et al.*, 2003] and a custom-made heuristic planner [Bonet and Geffner, 2001]. In addition to simulation of standard planning domains, it also includes an ROS interface to physical robots (i.e., a Baxter humanoid robot) and the Gazebo physics simulator.

At the object level, the cycle achieves goals that change the environment. At the metalevel, the cycle achieves goals that change the object level. That is, the metacognitive “perception” components introspectively monitor the processes and mental state changes in cognition. Monitoring occurs by reasoning over traces of object-level behavior (e.g., decision making and inferences). The “action” component consists of a metalevel controller that mediates reasoning over an abstract representation of the object-level cognition. It can manage the activity at the object level by changing the object-level goals or by changing MIDCA’s domain knowledge (e.g., SHOP action models).

4 Formalizing Metacognitive Expectations

We define a model of the metalevel, M_Σ , in an analogous manner of the action model, Σ , used in planning: $\Sigma = (S, A, \gamma)$, where S is the set of states that the agent can visit, A is the collection of actions that the agent can take and γ is the state-action transition function $\gamma : S \times A \rightarrow S$. Let $M_\Sigma = (S_M, A_M, \gamma_M)$ where S_M is a collection of mental states, A_M is a collection of mental actions, and γ_M is a transition function defined as $\gamma_M : S_M \times A_M \rightarrow S_M$.

A mental state is a vector of variables, $\langle v_1, \dots, v_n \rangle$. The variables that comprise a mental state are dependent on the agent; in MIDCA we use a separate variable for each of the following datums: *Selected Goals*, *Pending Goals*, *Current Plan*, *World State*, *Discrepancies*, *Explanations*, *Actions*. Thus our mental state is represented as a vector of length $n = 7$ as follows: $(g_c, \hat{G}, \pi, M_\Psi, D, E, \alpha_i)$. We make no constraints on the type of data for a mental state variable.

A mental action may perform reads or updates to variables in a mental state. MIDCA employs the following mental actions: *Perceive*, *Detect Discrepancies*, *Explanation*, *Goal Insertion* (i.e., updates the set of goals \hat{G} to be achieved), *Eval-*

uate (i.e., checks to see if the state M_Ψ entails the current goal g_c , and if so, removes it from \hat{G}), *Intend* (i.e., selects a new g_c from \hat{G}), *Plan* (i.e., calls a planner to generate a plan π to achieve g_c), and *Act* (i.e., executes the next step α_i from π). MIDCA enforces a strict sequence of mental actions that repeats (e.g. *Perceive* is always followed by *Detect Discrepancies*, *Act* is always followed by *Perceive*).

A mental trace, τ , is a sequence of mental states and mental actions interleaved. Specifically $\tau = \langle s_{M0}, \alpha_{M1}, s_{M1}, \alpha_{M2}, \dots, \alpha_{Mn}, s_{Mn} \rangle$ where $s_{M0}, \dots, s_{Mn} \in S_M$ and $\alpha_{M1}, \dots, \alpha_{Mn} \in A_M$. When the sequence of mental actions is fixed (as is the case in MIDCA), a trace may be represented as only the mental states $\tau = \langle s_{M0}, s_{M1}, \dots, s_{Mn} \rangle$. However, for the purpose of demonstrating the importance of the interaction of mental actions and mental states, we will use the representation of interleaved mental actions and mental states when describing metacognitive expectations.

We define a metacognitive expectation, $EX_M(s_{M_i}, \alpha_{M_i}, s_{M_{i+1}})$, over a segment of a mental trace τ . The length of the segment is always 3: prior mental state, s_{M_i} , mental action, α_{M_i} , and subsequent mental state, $s_{M_{i+1}}$. Since a mental action can read the value of a mental state and update that variable given its original value, the mental state before and after a mental action are relevant to the expectation (thus the τ segment length of 3). The metacognitive expectation is a Boolean function, $EX_M : (s_{M_i}, \alpha_{M_i}, s_{M_{i+1}}) \rightarrow \{true, false\}$. If the output is true, the expectation is met. Otherwise, the expectation is not met.

We now give an example of a metacognitive expectation that represents the following notion: *when the agent encounters a discrepancy, then the agent will generate an explanation for this discrepancy*. Formally this is expressed as follows: $EX_M(s_{M_i}, Explanation, s_{M_{i+1}})$ is a function that checks $v_{explanations} \neq \emptyset$ in $s_{M_{i+1}}$ whenever $v_{discrepancies} \neq \emptyset$ in s_{M_i} . For example, at the object level when MIDCA detects a discrepancy between the expected outcome of an action and the observed state, then an explanation for this object-level discrepancy must be generated. If the agent executes the action to move east and MIDCA observes that the agent remains in the same place, MIDCA might generate an explanation that the agent is stuck and generate a new goal to become \neg stuck. In our experiments, at some point during execution, strong winds will permanently affect the agent’s move-east action, causing it to move not only one cell east but also an additional 3 cells to the east. When this happens, MIDCA cannot generate any plausible explanation for this discrepancy at the object level. This triggers a discrepancy with the metacognitive expectation because no explanation at the ground-level was generated. In the next section we describe the MIDCA procedure and indicate how MIDCA deals with this discrepancy of metacognitive expectations.

5 Reasoning with Metacognitive Expectations

In the MIDCA architecture, mental traces are automatically generated when cognitive processes are executed at the object level. Algorithm 1 illustrates the procedure for capturing

Algorithm 1 The γ_M procedure that creates a mental trace τ . The expression $head|tail$ prepends the element $head$ to the sequence $tail$.

```

1: global  $\tau$ 
2: procedure  $\gamma_M(process, args)$ 
3:    $process.in \leftarrow args$ 
4:    $process.out \leftarrow apply(process, args)$ 
5:   if  $now(t)$  then
6:      $process.time \leftarrow t$ 
7:    $\tau \leftarrow process.self|\tau$ 
8:    $\tau \leftarrow process.out|\tau$ 
9:   return( $process.out$ )

```

ing mental states and process execution. The gamma function is an implementation of γ_M described above. We assume here that the application of any cognitive process to an input state will output a result s_M in the appropriate format (i.e., a 7-tuple mental state). The input, output and time of invocation are recorded in self-referential object form for the process (Lines 3-6). The function $now(t)$ in Line 5 is a temporal predicate as defined in active logic [Anderson *et al.*, 2008], a kind of step logic. The process and then the output state are subsequently appended to the mental trace τ . Note that this assembles the mental trace in opposite order compared to the description in the previous section. However Algorithm 2 below will reverse the sequence. Finally Line 9 returns the output to complete the procedure.

After initialization of the basic metacognitive state (Line 8), cognition performs one phase (determined by Lines 9-12) of its action-perception cycle (i.e., executes the switch-case control structure in Lines 14-32) and then invokes metacognition (Line 33). Each clause in the switch returns a mental state as defined in the previous section but modifies only selective elements in the state. A t in any element’s position indicates that the value remains unchanged. For example, *perceive* assigns a value to the 4th element of the state (a percept \vec{p} representation of the environment denoted by Ψ) to be unioned into the model of the environment M_Ψ (see Line 16). The remaining six elements are not effected.

Note the parallel control structure between the cognitive and metacognitive cycles. Each includes a comprehension sequence of $\langle perceive/monitor, interpret, evaluate \rangle$ and a problem-solving sequence of $\langle intend, plan, act \rangle$. In contrast, the former uses γ_M to record a trace whereas the latter does not. Yet functionally they are very similar. The cognitive level interprets the percepts from the external environment; whereas, the metalevel interprets the current trace of the internal object level. Interpretation is actually composed of a GDA three-step process. It detects discrepancies, explains them, and uses the explanation to generate potential new goals to resolve the discrepancy. This is implemented by having *interpret* add *explain* to the head of the processes to be executed (Line 18) and then calling *detect* (Line 19). Explanation then prepends $goal - insertion$ to the procedure sequence (Line 21) and calls *explain* (Line 22).

Algorithm 2 describes the basic high-level flow of control for the MIDCA architecture. MIDCA initializes the internal

Algorithm 2 The MIDCA procedure. Note that each invocation of γ_M returns a cognitive 7-tuple. For brevity we indicate with the “t” symbol an element that does not change as a result of the output.

```

1: global  $\tau$ ,  $cycle$ 
2:  $cycle \leftarrow \langle perceive, interpret, eval, intend, plan, act \rangle$ 
3: procedure MIDCA( $\Psi$ )
4:    $g_c \leftarrow \emptyset; \hat{G} \leftarrow \emptyset$ 
5:    $\tau \leftarrow \langle \emptyset \rangle$  ▷ Initialize trace with  $s_{M0}$ 
6:   cognition( $\emptyset, \phi, cycle$ )

7: procedure COGNITION( $M_\Psi, \pi, procs$ )
8:    $\pi_M \leftarrow \phi; g_M \leftarrow \emptyset; \hat{G}_M \leftarrow \emptyset$ 
9:   if  $procs = \langle \rangle$  then
10:      $procs \leftarrow cycle$ 
11:    $next \leftarrow head(procs)$ 
12:    $procs \leftarrow tail(procs)$ 
13:
14:   switch  $next$  do
15:     case  $perceive$ 
16:        $(t, t, t, M_\Psi \cup \vec{p}, t, t, t) \leftarrow \gamma_M (perceive, (\Psi))$ 
17:     case  $interpret$ 
18:        $procs \leftarrow explain|procs$ 
19:        $(t, t, t, D, t, t) \leftarrow \gamma_M (detect, (\vec{p}, \pi))$ 
20:     case  $explain$ 
21:        $procs \leftarrow insertion|procs$ 
22:        $(t, t, t, t, E, t) \leftarrow \gamma_M (explain, (D, \pi))$ 
23:     case  $insertion$ 
24:        $(t, \hat{G}, t, t, t, t) \leftarrow \gamma_M (goal-insertion, (E, \pi))$ 
25:     case  $eval$ 
26:        $(t, \hat{G}, t, M_\Psi, t, t, t) \leftarrow \gamma_M (evaluate, (D, E, g_c))$ 
27:     case  $intend$ 
28:        $(g_c, t, t, t, t, t) \leftarrow \gamma_M (intend, (\hat{G}, \pi))$ 
29:     case  $plan$ 
30:        $(t, t, \pi', t, t, t, t) \leftarrow \gamma_M (plan, (M_\Psi, g_c, \pi))$ 
31:     case  $act$ 
32:        $(t, t, t, t, t, t, \alpha) \leftarrow \gamma_M (act, (\pi'))$ 

33:   metacognition( $M_\Psi, \emptyset, \pi', \tau, procs$ )

34: procedure METACOGNITION( $M_\Psi, M_\Omega, \pi, \tau, procs$ )
35:    $\tau' \leftarrow monitor(M_\Psi, \pi, reverse(\tau))$ 
36:    $D_M, E_M, \hat{G}_M \leftarrow meta-interpret(\tau', \pi_M)$ 
37:    $M_\Omega, \hat{G}_M \leftarrow meta-evaluate(D_M, E_M, g_M)$ 
38:   if  $\hat{G}_M = \emptyset$  then
39:     cognition( $M_\Psi, \pi, procs$ )
40:   else
41:      $g_M \leftarrow meta-intend(\hat{G}_M, \pi)$ 
42:      $\pi'_M \leftarrow meta-plan(M_\Omega, g_M, \pi)$ 
43:     controller( $\pi'_M$ )
44:     metacognition( $M_\Psi, M_\Omega, \pi'_M, \tau', procs$ )

```

state (Lines 4-6) and starts a cognitive cycle (Line 6). The mental trace τ is initialized to the sequence having the empty set as its only member. The empty set represents the initial mental state s_{M0} . It is empty because no perception has oc-

curred and thus no knowledge of the world yet exists.

If an expectation failure occurs (on Line 36, \hat{G}_M will not be empty), it attempts to repair itself; otherwise it calls cognition to continue. Note that the mental trace τ is reversed on Line 35 before passing to the *monitor* function given that it is constructed in the opposite order by Algorithm 1. Interpretation at the metalevel is performed as a three-step process as is the case with the object-level analogue. It is however performed in a single call on line 36, setting a discrepancy D_M if one exists from any metacognitive expectation, explaining D_M , and then formulating a new goal if necessary to change the object level. Line 37 performs evaluation on any goal from previous metalevel cycles, and then Line 38 checks to see if a discrepancy existed (it will if a new meta-level goal was formulated. If so, it performs goal selection with intend (Line 41), plans for the goal at Line 42 and executes the plan with the metalevel controller on Line 43. Metacognition is called again to perform evaluation on the results (Line 44).

Reconsidering the example at the end of the previous section, when MIDCA fails to generate an explanation at the object level because permanent changes in the wind conditions causes the agent to always be pushed an additional 3 cells whenever it moves east. Since no explanation is generated at the object level, it causes a discrepancy of a metacognitive expectation. In this case Line 36 will evaluate τ' , which will contain a sequence of the form $(s_{M_i}, Explanation, s_{M_{i+1}})$ with $v_{explanations} = \emptyset$ in $s_{M_{i+1}}$ and $v_{discrepancies} \neq \emptyset$ in s_{M_i} . This will detect the discrepancy and generate a new goal \hat{G}_M . Therefore the condition in Line 38 fails and the else code in Lines 41-44 is performed. Line 41 selects the new goal, g_M , to fix the domain theory (the new goal is generated during meta-interpret on Line 36 and is a member of the resulting \hat{G}_M). Line 42 generates a plan to modify the domain description (now the effects of the move east will correctly indicate that it will be pushed 3 additional cells to the right), the controller makes this change in the domain description (Line 43) and the process is re-started again.

6 Experimental Evaluation

We performed an ablation study of three agents in two domains. These domains are NBeacons and Aggressive Arsonist. NBeacons is a modification of the Marsworld domain used in [Dannenbauer and Munoz-Avila, 2015]. Aggressive Arsonist is a modification of the arsonist domain used in [Paisner *et al.*, 2014]. The motivation behind using and modifying both domains is to test robust agents in environments that change over time.

The NBeacons domain is unbounded, with an area of interest to the agent that is a square grid of 100 tiles. Scattered among the area of interest are a total of 10 beacons and 20 sand pits. Beacons and sand pits cannot be in the same tile. Beacons are deactivated until the agent, which must be on the same tile as the beacon, performs an activate-beacon action. Other actions available to the agent include navigation (move east, west, north, south) and push actions (to free an agent that has fallen into a sand pit). There are five push actions an agent must execute before it will become free to move. Figure 2 shows a part of an NBeacons domain and is centered around

the area of interest. Wind may push the agent outside the area of interest, in which case the agent will navigate back.

Figure 2: NBeacons Example Scenario. The symbol *a* represents the agent, integers between 0-9 are the locations of beacons, and *~* represents a sand pit

The primary difference of NBeacons compared to Marsworld, is the addition of wind. After a period of time, wind blows causing the agent to be instantaneously pushed extra tiles whenever it attempts to move in a specific direction. If the agent would be pushed through any tiles containing sand pits, the agent will become stuck in the sand pit. In our experiments, wind begins to take effect after 500 ticks at a strength of 3 (pushing the agent 3 extra tiles) and then increases to a strength of 4 after 1500 ticks. Wind causes the effects of the agent’s move action to be permanently altered for the rest of its execution. Due to wind, an agent will find itself in a location other than what it expected, sometimes ending up in a sand pit. Wind always blows in one direction. Without wind, an agent never ends up in a sand pit because it will plan around them. All agents perform heuristic planning with the heuristic straight-line distance. Agents are given goals to activate specific beacons. Beacons are deactivated after they are activated to ensure an agent always has an available goal.

The second domain, Aggressive Arsonist, is based on the Arsonist domain in [Paisner *et al.*, 2014]. This domain is a blocksworld domain with an unseen arsonist lighting blocks on fire. The agent is tasked with randomly generated goals to build towers of height 4. In the original Arsonist domain, fire reduces the score the agent gets for completing each goal (here we do not measure score, only goal achievement). When each agent detects fire, they generate goals to put out the fire before returning to block stacking. Each tick of the environment (i.e. every time the agent takes an action) there is 20% chance the arsonist will light a block on fire.

The primary difference between Aggressive Arsonist and

the original Arsonist is that after 400 ticks, the domain changes and the arsonist becomes more aggressive. Now every time the arsonist lights a block on fire he/she will instead light two adjacent blocks on fire. The type of fire is stronger, such that the agent can only douse the fires by putting out the bottom fire first (otherwise the bottom fire keeps the block above it lit).

All three agents, in both domains, are implemented using the MIDCA Cognitive Architecture, albeit with ablated components. The baseline agent, a re-planning only agent, checks to see if the goal was reached at the end of execution of its plan, and if not, re-plans. The second agent, a goal driven autonomy agent, uses expectations to determine when a discrepancy of the world occurs, followed by explanation, and finally goal formulation. Expectations use a state comparison approach described in [Dannenhauer and Munoz-Avila, 2015] and used in [Molineaux *et al.*, 2010]. Explanation is implemented as a mapping from discrepancies to goals. Thus our GDA agent in the NBeacons domain generates a goal to become free after it explains that the agent is stuck in a sand pit. When the GDA agent finds it has been blown off course (but not in a sand pit), it inserts the same beacon-activation goal it previously had, which triggers immediate planning in the agent’s new state.

The third agent contains the GDA mechanism of the previous agent (GDA at the cognitive level) along with metacognition enabling it to reason with meta expectations. These expectations include the expectation mentioned in the example earlier: an agent detecting a discrepancy should also have generated an explanation. When the cognitive GDA component, Explanation, fails to produce an explanation after observing the discrepancy (in NBeacons the discrepancy is being in an unexpected location, in Aggressive Arsonist the discrepancy is failing to put out a fire when there is a fire underneath the block) the metacognitive expectation is triggered and the agent generates a goal to update its domain model. Since the focus of this paper is on modeling expectations and using them to detect any anomalies across any area of cognition, we do not go into detail regarding operator learning. Research in learning action models for planning domains has a long history [Čertický, 2014; Wang, 1995; 1996; Yang *et al.*, 2007]. In this work, we use an oracle-like function that updates the appropriate action given the distance the agent was pushed by the wind (NBeacons) and using the failed action putoutfire (Aggressive Arsonist). Unlike the other two ablated agents, the metacognitive agent is able to update its model for the action affected by wind (i.e., when wind is blowing east, the move-east action is updated, in NBeacons).

Our hypothesis is that the agent equipped with metacognitive expectations will achieve the lowest execution cost compared to the GDA agent and the replanning agent. We expect that the GDA agent will immediately respond to discrepancies while the replanning agent waits for its current invalid plan to run out. The metacognitive agent will detect an explanation failure of its GDA components and update its effects its actions to take into account the changes in the domain (wind in NBeacons, stronger fires Aggressive Arsonist). For example, the GDA agent will be blown unexpectedly into

sand pits while the metacognitive agent will avoid them once it has learned from previous encounters with the wind.

7 Results

The results of both domains are averaged over 10 runs and shown in Figures 3 and 4. In NBeacons, each run places randomly the beacons and the sand pits with the agent starting in the center (see Figure 2 for an example). The x axis is the cumulative number of goals achieved and the y axis is the cumulative execution cost.

NBeacons. After 500 actions, wind begins blowing east with a strength of 3 (the agent will be pushed an additional 3 tiles), followed with another increase in wind to 4 after 1,500 actions. Prior to wind, the performance of all the agents is the same because they are able to plan around all sand pits (roughly when $y = 500$). However, once wind is introduced, the agents may be blown into a sand pit and must execute a series of push actions to free themselves, thus raising their execution costs to activate beacons. All agents exhibit a similar performance for the first 75 goals, which takes about 800 actions. Although wind is introduced after 500 actions, it takes some time to see the benefit because not all actions are affected by wind. (When wind is blowing east, only the move-east action is affected. Thus goals that do not require navigating east will not see any impact from wind).

Aggressive Arsonist. Each run starts with all blocks on the ground and no fires. After 400 ticks, the arsonist becomes aggressive, and lights stronger fires which cause two adjacent blocks to burn. Unlike NBeacons, shortly have this change in the domain, the replanning and GDA agents fail because they are unable to put out fires. This is due to repeated failures when trying to put out a fire on a block that has another burning block below it that is also on fire. Only the metacognitive agent identifies the explanation failure at the GDA level, and performs operator learning (in the same fashion as NBeacons) and learns two new operators for putting out fire (one that handles the case of a block on the ground, the other that handles the case of a block stacked on another block). By learning these new operators, the metacognitive agent is able to put out the fires and continue operating.

As the agent's continue to operate, we see that even when the effects of a single action change in the environment, metacognition improves performance over the replanning and the GDA agents by identifying a cognitive failure and addressing a limitation in the agent's own knowledge.

8 Conclusion

This work extends the existing research on anticipatory approaches to intelligent agents within a cognitive architecture that use expectations to focus problem solving on salient aspects of a problem. We introduce metacognitive expectations, a novel class of expectations that applies the approach to the problem-solving cycle itself rather than just the environment and actions executed within it. Using persistent domains, NBeacons and Aggressive Arsonist, that change over time, we provide empirical results showing the benefit of reasoning with metacognitive expectations. These metacognitive expectations are domain-independent; in our experiments with both

Figure 3: Average Execution Cost in NBeacons

Figure 4: Average Execution Cost in Aggressive Arsonist

the NBeacons and Aggressive Arsonist domains, a failure to explain a change in environment triggers a discrepancy to the same metacognitive expectation, showing the generality of this approach.

For future work we will study automated generation of metacognitive expectations. We will explore automated learning of expectations from traces of mental states. This will enable us to side-step the potentially difficult task of expressing mental actions such as "PLAN" in a declarative language. On the other hand it may require metacognitive agents that are capable of reasoning with multiple plausible expectations.

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